

EXTERIOR INDICATORS OF SHEEP AND THEIR SEASONAL VARIATIONS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the exterior characteristics of Karakul sheep and the morphological measurements of different ethological types. During the study, changes in height at withers, body oblique length, chest circumference and width, as well as cannon bone circumference were studied seasonally. The obtained results showed that the exterior parameters of animals are significantly related to their constitutional type. It was found that sheep belonging to the first ethological type had a significant advantage in all periods (after birth, after lamb separation, and during mating) compared to animals of the second and third types. Seasonal changes demonstrated an increase in body length, chest volume, and cannon bone circumference, reflecting the natural stages of animal development. The research results confirm the practical importance of exterior analysis in the processes of selection, breed quality evaluation, and productivity forecasting.*

Keywords: *Karakul sheep, exterior, body structure, constitution type, ethological type, morphological indicators, body proportions, seasonal variation, animal husbandry, morphometry, sheep breeds, selection, animal physiology, productivity indicators.*

Relevance of the topic. Although Karakul sheep are also distributed in other CIS countries, they are especially widespread in Turkmenistan. In the 1980s, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Ukraine, Moldova, and Kalmykia were among the major centers of Karakul breeding. However, in recent years, the number of sheep in these regions has sharply declined. Therefore, it is crucial to introduce modern selection methods and advanced technologies to increase the number and productivity of sheep in these areas. Uzbekistan, the homeland of the Karakul breed, ranks among the leading countries in the world in terms of herd size, color diversity, and genetic resources. The Sur Karakul sheep of Karakalpak type, which are especially valuable in the color gene pool, are raised only in Uzbekistan. In recent years, significant scientific research has been conducted to effectively utilize genetic potential; selection methods have been

developed, and 33 highly productive factory types and numerous breeding systems have been created.

Exterior refers to the external appearance of animals, the development level, and the shape characteristics of their body parts. It plays an important role in expressing the animal's constitution through external features. Although exterior is closely related to the constitution type, in some cases it may have independent significance. For example, animals with a strong constitution may differ in head size, neck length, or body height. Therefore, exterior serves as a key criterion in assessing the overall body structure and productive potential of animals.

The first scientific concept of exterior was introduced by the French scientist Claude Bourgel, who was the first to bring the term "exterior" into zootechnical practice.

Research Objective. The aim of the study is to investigate the biological and productive characteristics of Sur Karakul sheep under the natural and climatic conditions of the Takhtakupyr district, to scientifically assess the efficiency of processing their products, and to identify ways to introduce advanced methods into production processes[3.4].

Research Methods. The evaluation of lamb pelts obtained from experimental sheep was carried out based on the *Manual on Breeding Work and Lamb Evaluation in Karakul Sheep Breeding*. Numerical data were processed statistically using variational statistical methods in accordance with the *Manual on Biometry for Zootechnicians* [1.2].

From this perspective, identifying the biological characteristics of animals is crucial for studying their adaptability and maximum productivity performance. During the research, the exterior characteristics of Sur Karakul sheep belonging to different ethological types were analyzed by season. Measurements were carried out in three stages:

1. After birth (March)
2. After lamb separation (July)
3. During mating period (October)

Measured parameters included:

- Height at withers
- Oblique body length
- Chest circumference
- Chest width
- Chest depth
- Cannon bone (shank) circumference

Research Results. According to the analysis, sheep belonging to the first ethological type showed significantly higher results in all periods compared to the second and third types. The summarized data are presented in Table 1.

The superiority in height at withers was determined as follows:

- After birth – 1.14 and 2.87 cm ($P < 0.001$)
- After lamb separation – 0.90 and 2.64 cm ($P < 0.001$)
- During mating – 1.31 and 2.53 cm ($P < 0.001$)

In terms of oblique body length, the first type of sheep also showed advantage:

- After birth – 1.39 and 2.77 cm
- After lamb separation – 1.50 and 2.76 cm
- During mating – 1.21 and 2.72 cm ($P < 0.001$)

Chest circumference, width, and depth were also significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) in sheep of the first ethological type.

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Table 1

Exterior indicators of sheep and their seasonal changes

Ethological type	n	Studied period	Exterior indicators, cm (X±Sx)					
			Height at withers	Oblique body length	Chest circumference	Chest width	Thoracic depth	Cannon bone circumference
I	30	After birth (March)	65,28±0,22	66,34±0,23	83,72±0,22	16,81±0,09	30,21±0,08	7,79±0,03
II	30		64,14±0,19 ^{x)}	64,95±0,22 ^{x)}	81,46±0,21 ^{x)}	16,19±0,09 ^{x)}	29,81±0,08 ^{x)}	7,69±0,03 ^{x)}
III	30		62,41±0,19 ^{x)}	63,57±0,21 ^{x)}	79,93±0,20 ^{x)}	15,89±0,08 ^{x)}	28,78±0,07 ^{x)}	7,61±0,03 ^{x)}
I	30	After lambs were weaned (July)	65,92±0,21	66,71±0,22	84,47±0,21	17,64±0,09	30,85±0,09	8,00±0,04
II	30		65,02±0,20 ^{x)}	65,21±0,22	82,63±0,20 ^{x)}	16,89±0,09 ^{x)}	30,31±0,09 ^{x)}	7,83±0,05
III	30		63,28±0,20 ^{x)}	63,95±0,21 ^{x)}	80,75±0,21 ^{x)}	16,11±0,08 ^{x)}	29,21±0,07 ^{x)}	7,70±0,02 ^{x)}
I	30	During the mating period (October)	66,52±0,20	67,2±0,22	85,93±0,23	18,51±0,09	31,56±0,09	8,14±0,04
II	30		65,21±0,19 ^{x)}	66,04±0,22 ^{x)}	83,56±0,23 ^{x)}	17,42±0,09 ^{x)}	30,71±0,11 ^{x)}	8,03±0,03 ^{x)}
III	30		63,99±0,18 ^{x)}	64,53±0,21 ^{x)}	81,79±0,20 ⁾	16,77±0,08 ^{x)}	29,91±0,08 ^{x)}	7,91±0,03 ^{x)}

Statistical analysis results were assessed at significance levels of $P < 0.001$ and $P < 0.05$

Cannon bone circumference indicators confirmed the better physical development of type I sheep, showing reliable differences at $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.001$ levels.

Discussion. The analysis of exterior parameters allows determining the development degree of various body parts. Correlation coefficients between certain morphometric measurements are calculated to assess their interrelationships. However, absolute measurements alone cannot fully describe the exterior. Therefore, it is often advisable to express these values as percentages relative to a main parameter, such as height at withers or body length. In practice, using body length as a reference is biologically sound and provides higher accuracy.

Conclusions.

1. The exterior indicators of Sur Karakul sheep belonging to the first ethological type were higher than those of other types, indicating their better-developed body structure.
2. A gradual increase in exterior parameters was observed with the change of seasons, reflecting the natural process of growth and development.
3. Exterior analysis can serve as an important diagnostic tool in determining the constitution and productive potential of animals.

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